

ANALYSIS OF GDP DYNAMICS AND STRUCTURE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. In recent decades, global interest in comparing key macroeconomic indicators such as Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and national income has significantly increased. This growth in interest is mainly due to the expansion of international economic relations, deepening integration processes, and the strengthening of global cooperation. This article analyzes the recent development trends of Uzbekistan's economy, the role of the service sector in GDP, and its comparison with global economic patterns. The study also highlights the role of international organizations such as the UN, OECD, and the World Bank in facilitating cross-country economic comparisons.

Keywords: Gross Domestic Product, international comparison, macroeconomic indicators, Uzbekistan's economy, service sector, World Bank, United Nations, economic integration

Introduction. In recent years, interest in comparing the most important macroeconomic indicators such as gross domestic product, national income, and others at the international level has increased worldwide. This interest has grown due to the expansion of external economic relations, deepening of integration processes, and strengthening of international economic cooperation. For every country in the world, it is important to know what role their country plays in the global and regional economy and how their economy compares with the economies of other countries with whom they cooperate or compete in global markets. Therefore, they need to organize comparisons of macroeconomic indicators across different countries or respond with readiness to participate in proposals for such comparisons. The most important organizations showing the greatest activity in this field are the UN, OECD, World Bank, and others. They need to compare information on the most important macroeconomic indicators at the international level to solve problems related to establishing various forms of international economic cooperation. Analyzing development trends of the world and regional economy, solving practical problems, helping countries achieve social and economic development goals, providing loans, financing joint projects, determining the share of contributions to budgets of organizations and countries is impossible without considering this information. International organizations

also use comparable GDP data to analyze the impact of various factors on economic growth rates. They act as organizers and coordinators in this area. For example, within the framework of the UN organization's activities, there is an International Comparison Program (ICP) project. Its calculations within the framework of global comparisons made it possible to directly rank countries in terms of their volume in the world economy, as well as in terms of gross domestic product per capita. Later, comparisons began to be carried out within individual regions of the world (Europe, Asia, Africa, etc.), and subsequently the obtained regional results were used to calculate world comparison indices. Summarizing all of the above, we can confidently say that the issue of international comparison of gross domestic product is quite relevant and arouses scientific and practical interest.

Countries with transition economies, usually 28 states of Central and Eastern Europe and the former USSR transitioning from centrally planned to market economies, and in some cases Mongolia, China, and Vietnam, are included. Based on countries with transition economies, Uzbekistan is usually considered separately, not connected with other groups, due to its political significance (2% of world gross domestic product and 1% of exports). A separate group includes the Central and Eastern European countries that were once part of the socialist camp, as well as the former USSR states, called the former "ruble" zone countries, which have economies in transition.

Analysis of GDP Dynamics and Structure in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

According to the results of January-September 2024, the volume of GDP of the Republic of Uzbekistan amounted to 1,015,331.8 billion soums at current prices and increased by 6.6% compared to January-September 2023. The GDP deflator index amounted to 113.1% relative to the prices of January-September 2023. The volume of gross value added created in all sectors of the economy amounted to 95.4% of the total GDP volume and increased by 6.6% (the impact on the absolute growth of GDP was 6.3 percentage points). The share of net taxes on products in the GDP structure amounted to 4.6% and increased by 6.6% compared to January-September 2023 (the impact on the absolute growth of GDP was -0.3 p.p.). According to the results of January-September 2024, minor changes were observed in the GDP structure. The share of the service sector in GDP (GVA) increased from 46.5% to 47.2%, and the share of industry increased from 24.7% to 26.2%. At the same time, the share of agriculture, forestry and fishery decreased from 21.2% to 19.4%, and the share of the construction sector decreased from 7.6% to 7.2%.

According to the results of January-September 2024, a positive growth rate of 3.1% was recorded in agriculture, forestry and fishery (in January-September 2023 - 4.0%, in January-September 2022 - 3.6%, in January-September 2021 - 4.0%, in January-September 2020 - 2.6%). Volume, billion soums, growth rate, % compared to the same period of the previous year. For information: in January-September 2024, the total volume of agricultural, forestry and fishery products (services) amounted to 323,878.0 billion soums. 97.5% of the total volume of agricultural, forestry and fishery products (services) was accounted for by crop production and livestock, hunting and services provided in these sectors, 1.9% - forestry, 0.6% - fishery.

According to the results of January-September 2024, the positive growth rates in this sector are related to the increase of 3.1% in crop production and livestock, hunting and services provided in these sectors, 2.9% in forestry, and 1.3% in fishery. In January-September 2024, compared to January-September 2023, the volume of construction work increased by 9.0%. In particular, the growth rates amounted to 108.6% in the construction of buildings and structures, 112.5% in the construction of civil facilities, and 106.4% in specialized construction works. For information: in January-September 2024, the volume of construction work amounted to 167,101.2 billion soums. In the total volume of construction works, the share of large construction organizations was 24.4%, the share of small enterprises and microfirms was 48.1%, and the share of individuals was 27.5%.

According to the results of January-September 2024, the gross value added of the service sector amounted to 457,899.8 billion soums and increased by 7.5% compared to January-September 2023. In particular, trade services increased by 11.1%, accommodation and food services by 10.6%, transportation and storage services by 8.7%, information and communication services by 22.3%, and other services by 4.5%.

According to the results of January-September 2024, the share of the transportation and storage sector in the GDP of the Republic of Uzbekistan amounted to 5.3%. The largest share in the value added of the transportation and storage sector was road transport, which amounted to 53.0%. The share of pipeline transport in the total value added of this sector was 14.7%, rail transport - 9.1%, auxiliary transport activities - 15.0%, and air transport - 8.2%. In January-September 2024, the share of the information and communication sector in the country's economy amounted to 2.6%. The main share in the gross value added of this sector was communication services (wired and mobile communication

services, Internet network, etc.), which amounted to 37.1%. The remaining 62.9% of the gross value added created in the sector was accounted for by other branches of information and communication (publishing activities, activities in the field of computer programming, activities in software development, television and radio broadcasting, etc.).

According to the results of January-September 2024, the volume of gross value added of the unobserved (informal and hidden) economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan amounted to 357,507.6 billion soums and its share in gross domestic product was 35.2%. Of this, the volume of gross value added of the informal economy amounted to 274,028.6 billion soums and its share in gross domestic product was 27.0%. The volume of gross value added of the hidden economy amounted to 83,479.1 billion soums and its share in gross domestic product was 8.2%.

Unobserved economy - types of economic activities that are not fully or partially covered by permanent statistical observations, as well as those assessed in statistical indicators using indirect methods. Informal economy - economic activities related to production (provision of services) carried out by households or individuals without registration in the prescribed manner. Hidden economy - economic activities that are not prohibited by law, but are deliberately concealed from government bodies for the purpose of tax evasion and non-compliance with the requirements of legal documents.

Conclusions. According to the results of January-September 2024 of the Republic of Uzbekistan, stable growth rates were observed in the economy. The GDP volume amounted to 1,015,331.8 billion soums, increasing by 6.6% compared to the same period of the previous year. In this growth, the service sector, industry and construction sectors played a leading role. The fact that the share of the service sector in GDP reached 47.2% indicates that diversification processes in the economy are consistently continuing. In particular, the 22.3% growth of information and communication services shows the positive results of digital economy development. At the same time, the decrease in the share of agriculture emphasizes the need to increase efficiency in the agricultural sector.

The analysis shows that the construction sector, growing by 9%, is becoming one of the important drivers in the economy. The fact that the share of large construction organizations is 24.4% plays an important role in the development of the country's infrastructure. However, the fact that the informal and hidden economy remains at a high level with a share of 35.2% indicates the need to strengthen measures to increase economic transparency.

It is recommended that, to ensure the quality of economic growth: first, it is necessary to widely introduce innovations in the service sector and increase attention to the development of digital technologies; second, it is important to apply modern agricultural technologies to increase productivity in agriculture; third, to reduce the volume of the informal economy, it is necessary to simplify the taxation system and increase the financial literacy of the population. In addition, continuing modernization processes based on the principles of environmental sustainability in all sectors of the economy remains an important strategic direction for Uzbekistan.

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